

Electrostrictive Metamaterial Study: Shaping Fields to Exceed Intrinsic Material Limits

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Short title

Shaping Fields in Electrostrictors

Abstract

Electrostrictive actuators are attractive for micro-positioning and adaptive optics due to their reliability, but they face a trade-off between stroke, internal stress, and directional control. Increasing stroke typically amplifies stress and off-axis deformation, while material tuning in relaxor ferroelectrics such as PMN–PT–BT yields limited device-level gains. Here, we demonstrate two electrostrictive metamaterials (Design-1 and Design-2) that overcome this trade-off through shape-based electric-field routing. Architected PMN–PT–BT unit cells with compliant-hinge geometries were analyzed using a fully coupled ferroelectroelastic finite-element model. Compared to a solid slab, motion per unit input energy increased by $\sim 16\times$ (Design-1) and $\sim 11\times$ (Design-2), while stroke per unit internal stress nearly doubled. Directionality improved by $\sim 3\times$, with the strongly guided surface fraction increasing from $\sim 22.7\%$ to $\sim 61\text{--}64.5\%$. Geometric field routing reduced high-stress tails, enabling safe-bias operation at $\sim 2.4\text{--}3.2\times$ lower average polarization and increasing the effective electrostrictive coefficient (Q^{eff}) by $\sim 1.7\times$ in Design-2.

Teaser

Architected metamaterials route electric fields to boost stroke per energy while reducing stress and off-axis motion.

1 Introduction

Background: Electromechanical coupling mechanisms

The ability to convert electrical energy into mechanical motion is a cornerstone of modern technology, driving devices from precision actuators to acoustic transducers [1, 2]. This capability, known as electromechanical coupling, is primarily governed by two distinct phenomena in solid-state materials: piezoelectricity and electrostriction [3, 4]. Piezoelectricity is a linear effect, where mechanical strain (S) is directly proportional to the applied electric field (E), described as $S_{ij} = d_{kij}E_k$. However, this powerful effect is restricted by crystal symmetry. It can only exist in the 20 out of 32 crystallographic point groups that lack a center of inversion [2, 5]. In contrast,

electrostriction is a universal, quadratic phenomenon present in all dielectric materials, regardless of their crystal symmetry. It is fundamentally described as a coupling between strain and electric polarization (P), $S_{ij} = Q_{ijkl}P_kP_l$. In linear dielectrics, this is often phenomenologically defined by the electric field as $S_{ij} = M_{ijkl}E_kE_l$ [6, 7].

In acentric materials, where both piezoelectric and electrostrictive strains may be observed, the linear piezoelectric effect dominates the electromechanical response [8, 9]. This is due to the relative magnitudes of the material coefficients. The piezoelectric coefficient d (on the order of 300–600 pC N⁻¹ for common lead zirconate titanate (PZT) ceramics [10]) typically yields a much larger strain than the electrostrictive coefficient M (often 10⁻¹⁶ m² V⁻² or less) at practical field levels [11, 12].

The case for electrostrictive relaxors

However, this dynamic shifts completely in relaxor ferroelectrics, such as lead magnesium niobate–lead titanate (PMN-PT). In these materials, the electrostrictive response can be dominant, particularly when operated in their high-temperature, centrosymmetric paraelectric phase. In this phase, the linear piezoelectric effect is absent by symmetry [8, 13–15]. More importantly, the mechanism is distinct. Conventional piezoelectricity relies on the movement of domain walls, a process that results in significant hysteresis, creep, and material fatigue [2, 16]. Conversely, electrostriction is proportional to the square of the field. It produces strain independent of the field’s polarity [8, 15] (Fig. 1) and exhibits very low hysteresis (often < 5%) [17, 18]. This makes it far more suitable for high-precision applications like micro-positioning devices [19–23] and adaptive optics [24, 25]. These applications cannot tolerate the non-linearity (hysteresis) and instability (creep and fatigue) of traditional piezoelectrics [11].

The reason this electrostrictive response becomes exceptionally large in relaxors is due to their unique nanoscale structure. Relaxors contain polar nanoregions (PNRs) that are easily reoriented or grown by an external field [6, 7, 26]. This high degree of polarizability leads to a colossal macroscopic dielectric permittivity (ϵ_r), often exceeding 10³ [27]. Because the field-related electrostriction coefficient M scales with the square of permittivity ($M \approx Q \cdot \epsilon_0^2(\epsilon_r - 1)^2$), the resulting strain in relaxors becomes massive. This offers a path to large, stable, and precise

Figure 1: Macroscopic electrostriction showing deformation independent of electric field polarity. (a) No field ($E = 0$). (b) Field in $+x$. (c) Field in $-x$. A positive Q_{xxxx} causes longitudinal expansion and transverse contraction, while a negative Q_{xxxx} reverses these effects.

actuation that conventional piezoelectrics cannot match [13, 26, 28, 29].

Related work: From material tuning to geometric engineering

Historically, efforts to further enhance this response have focused on material-level optimization [9, 12, 20, 21, 23, 30, 31]. This includes difficult and time-consuming chemical processes, such as precisely engineering compositions near a morphotropic phase boundary (MPB) [9, 26] or the complex, costly growth of large-scale single crystals [30, 32]. A powerful alternative to these chemistry-bound limitations is the use of metamaterials. These are artificial structures whose geometry is engineered to produce effective properties not found in the constituent bulk material. Initial studies in metamaterials led to breakthroughs like materials with a negative Poisson’s ratio [33, 34] and negative refractive indices [35]. These advances enabled the design of invisibility cloaks [36] and perfect lenses [37]. Over the past decade, these ideas crossed into the electromechanical media. Piezoelectric metamaterials now manipulate elastic waves [38], tune programmable vibrational bandgaps [39–41], and harvest energy from ambient vibrations [42, 43]. Most notably, architectures have been used to engineer effective piezoelectric coefficients that are dramatically enhanced [44].

Current limitations and research gaps

Despite this broad progress, two significant gaps remain. First, the field remains overwhelmingly piezo-centric. Explicitly electrostriction-focused architectures are comparatively rare. Only a few theoretical works suggest that composite designs could magnify the apparent electrostrictive response beyond the limits of the constituent materials [45, 46]. Second, a primary application for high-response electrostrictive materials is actuation, but a larger stroke almost always comes at the cost of high internal mechanical stress and unwanted off-axis motion. This stress often concentrates at sharp geometric features or electrode edges. This leads to micro-cracking, mechanical fatigue, and catastrophic device failure long before the material’s intrinsic strain limit is reached [4, 19, 47].

Contributions

In this study, we introduce and investigate two metamaterial designs, Design-1 and Design-2, derived through exploration, that function as “stress-quiet” actuators. These architectures use geometry to strategically manage internal field distributions. This approach achieves an enhanced electrostrictive response with very low off-axis motion, while simultaneously reducing peak internal stresses. The behavior of these geometries was analyzed through device-level, surface-averaged metrics and compared to a monolithic slab design using a fully-coupled 2-dimensional finite element model (FEM) in COMSOL Multiphysics.

In this work, we: (i) outline the approach and modeling choices; (ii) describe the geometry design strategy for routing fields and releasing stress; (iii) present the results and discussion, including quantitative gains in actuation per stress, energy-aware motion, and effective electrostrictive coefficients; (iv) discuss the conclusions, the implications of stress-quiet actuation, the limitations of this study, and future work; and (v) detail the methods used, including finite element model parameters and material properties.

2 Results and Discussion

2.1 Overview of the Approach

To isolate the effect of geometry on the electro-mechanical response, we study three distinct unit cell designs:

Figure 2: Study setup: a slab, Design 1 (D1) and Design 2 (D2), all driven by the same voltage $V_0 = V_{max} \sin(2\pi t)$, where $V_{max} = 200$ V.

1. A solid, monolithic slab (as a baseline).
2. Design 1 (D1), an architected cell.
3. Design 2 (D2), a second architected cell.

As illustrated in Fig. 2, all three geometries are composed of the same electrostrictive material—a ternary solid solution of lead magnesium niobate (PMN), lead titanate (PT), and barium titanate (BT) (PMN–PT–BT)—and are subjected to identical electrical boundary conditions. The specific material parameters for PMN–PT–BT are held constant across all three designs and are listed in Supplementary Table S1.

For this comparison, the bottom portions are held at ground (0 V), while the top portions are driven by a sinusoidal voltage, $V_0(t) = V_{max} \sin(2\pi t)$, with $V_{max} = 200$ V.

This comparative setup allows us to attribute any differences in electro-mechanical performance (such as actuation, internal stress, and motion directionality) purely to the unit cell’s shape and architecture.

2.2 Design and field distribution strategy

Our core strategy is to use geometry—specifically compliant-hinge pathways—to steer the internal electric field and polarization \mathbf{P} . This allows us to tailor the site of electrostrictive strain generation and control how it translates into macroscopic displacement (Fig. 3). Compliant joints are a standard way to guide motion and strain flow. They aggregate many small local deformations into a single useful output, a design idea formalized in the compliant-mechanisms literature [48].

In our baseline slab, the field is mostly uniform. Consequently, the polarization is spatially delocalized. Under the quadratic electrostriction law ($\mathbf{S} \propto \mathbf{P}^2$), this activates strain broadly rather than concentrating it where it is most useful.

By contrast, our ring–link layout with narrow, compliant hinge structures the field. It channels \mathbf{P} into selected paths, such as the flexure hinges and the auxetic-strut motif (Fig. 3).

Figure 3: Geometric control of electric field distribution for enhanced electrostrictive response.

In these regions, local increases in \mathbf{P} translate via the quadratic law into larger local \mathbf{S} . The hinges then aggregate these local strains into a coherent global motion. Interface-engineered oxides demonstrate this principle at the materials scale. In these materials, localized strain and symmetry breaking at the interface drive exceptionally large electrostriction. This underscores why routing fields is critical [31].

This choice of architecture, rather than material change, follows a common pattern in architected systems. Geometry can guide and concentrate energy along intended routes while relaxing it where it is less useful. In piezo systems, circular auxetic substrates illustrate how negative-Poisson-ratio layouts direct deformation to productive regions without altering the underlying material [43]. Likewise, GRIN (gradient-index) metamaterials—structures whose effective properties vary smoothly in space—are used to guide and focus waves [40]. We apply this same idea at quasi-static bias.

In our designs, the compliant ring-and-hinge network routes polarization and strain toward the actuation axis. Simultaneously, it softens the response near free edges and tight curvatures. This supports cleaner, more directed motion. Quantitative evidence for this behavior is reported in the next section.

2.3 Electrostriction gain and safe-bias efficiency

We first verify that the device-level electrostriction follows the expected quadratic law. To quantify this, we fit no-intercept lines to the surface-averaged strain and polarization-squared terms (Fig. 4), where the slopes yield the effective electrostrictive coefficients, Q^{eff} (Table 1a). The relations exhibit high linearity ($R^2 \approx 1.000$) for all geometries, confirming the macroscopic $S \propto P^2$ relationship is preserved. The architected geometry of Design 2 (D2) enhances the actuation-axis coefficient, Q_{11}^{eff} , to a value $\sim 1.72\times$ that of the non-architected slab. This increase indicates a higher strain generation per unit of polarization squared, a result of the geometry-driven field routing.

Next, we quantify the effect of geometry on electromechanical efficiency. The architected unit cells demonstrate improved conversion of input energy to displacement. The energy-aware figure of merit, $\langle |u| \rangle_S / U_{\text{in}}$, increases by $\sim 16\times$ for Design 1 (D1) and $\sim 11\times$ for D2 compared to the

Table 1: Summary of electromechanical performance at peak drive ($t^* = 0.25$). Values in subtables are the quantities referenced in the main text; full tables are provided in Supplementary Materials (Tables S2–S5).

(a) Effective longitudinal electrostriction coefficient Q_{11}^{eff} (obtained from no-intercept quadratic fits of surface-averaged axial strain vs. polarization) and energy-aware motion efficiency proxy $\langle |u| \rangle_S / U_{\text{in}}$ (surface-averaged displacement magnitude per total input energy per cycle), both normalized to the slab reference.

Geometry	Q_{11}^{eff} ($\text{m}^4 \text{C}^{-2}$)	$Q_{11}^{\text{eff}}/\text{Slab}$	$\langle u \rangle_S / U_{\text{in}}$ ($\mu\text{m J}^{-1}$)	$(\langle u \rangle_S / U_{\text{in}}) / \text{Slab}$
Slab	$1.330\,000 \times 10^{-2}$	1.000	2.096×10^3	1.000
Design-1	$1.042\,843 \times 10^{-2}$	0.784	3.386×10^4	16.154
Design-2	$2.288\,095 \times 10^{-2}$	1.720	2.355×10^4	11.235

(b) Surface-averaged actuation per unit average von Mises stress: ratio of surface-averaged displacement magnitude $\langle |u| \rangle_S$ to surface-averaged von Mises stress $\langle \sigma_{\text{VM}} \rangle_S$, normalized to the slab reference.

Geometry	$\langle u \rangle_S / \langle \sigma_{\text{VM}} \rangle_S$ ($\mu\text{m m}^2 \text{N}^{-1}$)	$(\langle u \rangle_S / \langle \sigma_{\text{VM}} \rangle_S) / \text{Slab}$
Slab	2.266×10^{-8}	1.000
Design-1	4.401×10^{-8}	1.942
Design-2	4.520×10^{-8}	1.995

(c) Directionality of surface displacement at peak drive phase ($t^* = 0.25$): area-weighted percentage of surface elements where the transverse-to-axial displacement ratio $r = |u_y|/|u_x|$ exceeds the thresholds 5 and 100 (the $r > 100$ column uses the full untrimmed dataset).

Geometry	% area with $r = u_y / u_x > 5$	% area with $r > 100$
Slab	22.727	0.50
Design-1	61.434	9.04
Design-2	64.495	8.98

slab (Table 1a). This improved efficiency permits operation at lower internal polarization levels. As shown in Fig. 5b, at peak drive ($t^* = 0.25$), comparable stroke is achieved with an average actuation-axis polarization $\langle |P_y| \rangle_S$ that is $2.4\times$ (D1) and $3.2\times$ (D2) lower than the slab. These results show that geometric architecting can simultaneously increase the effective electrostrictive gain and improve the motion per unit of input energy, thereby widening the safe operational window by reducing the required average polarization.

Figure 4: No-intercept linear fits on surface-averaged quantities; slopes and R^2 are reported in Supplementary Table S2.

2.4 Stress-quiet actuation

We now quantify the surface stress distribution at peak drive ($t^* = 0.25$) and evaluate the stroke obtained per unit of average stress. For this quantification, we convert the finite-element fields at $t^* = 0.25$ into an area-weighted stress distribution. For every surface triangle e with vertices at positions \mathbf{x}_i , \mathbf{x}_j , and \mathbf{x}_ℓ and nodal von Mises values $\sigma_{\text{VM},i}$, $\sigma_{\text{VM},j}$, and $\sigma_{\text{VM},\ell}$, we formed an element-level stress by nodal averaging

$$\sigma_{\text{VM}}^{(e)} = \frac{\sigma_{\text{VM},i} + \sigma_{\text{VM},j} + \sigma_{\text{VM},\ell}}{3}, \quad (1)$$

and its physical area

$$A^{(e)} = \frac{1}{2} |(\mathbf{x}_j - \mathbf{x}_i) \times (\mathbf{x}_\ell - \mathbf{x}_i)|. \quad (2)$$

Using a pooled 0–99.5% stress range common to all three geometries, we then computed, for each bin B_k ,

$$p_k = \frac{1}{A_{\text{tot}}} \sum_{e: \sigma_{\text{VM}}^{(e)} \in B_k} A^{(e)}, \quad A_{\text{tot}} = \sum_e A^{(e)}, \quad (3)$$

so that the plotted quantity is percent of total area per bin. On top of each curve we overlaid two area-weighted scalars,

$$\langle \sigma_{\text{VM}} \rangle = \frac{1}{A_{\text{tot}}} \sum_e A^{(e)} \sigma_{\text{VM}}^{(e)}, \quad (4)$$

$$\sigma_{\text{VM},95} : \sum_{e: \sigma_{\text{VM}}^{(e)} \leq \sigma_{\text{VM},95}} A^{(e)} = 0.95 A_{\text{tot}}, \quad (5)$$

which are shown in the plot (Fig. 5a) as the dashed (area-weighted mean) and dotted (area-weighted 95th-percentile) vertical lines.

The resulting distributions (Fig. 5a) differentiate the slab from the architected cells. The slab histogram is broader and possesses a longer high-stress tail, indicating that a larger fraction of its surface operates near the local material limit. In contrast, Design 1 shifts the majority of its surface area into lower-stress bins, and its area-weighted 95th-percentile stress is lower than

Figure 5: (a) Elementwise von Mises stress distribution across geometries at peak drive ($t^* = 0.25$). Surface triangles are binned over a shared 0–99.5% stress range, and bars report percent of total area per bin. Dashed lines mark the area-weighted mean stress; dotted lines mark the area-weighted 95th-percentile stress. Both architected designs shift area into lower-stress bins and shorten the high-stress tail compared with the slab, evidencing stress reduction by geometry. (b) Safe-bias actuation: motion maintained with lower average polarisation.

that of the slab. This result suggests the compliant load paths are effective at redistributing stress. Design 2 exhibits the same trend to a lesser degree. This suppression of the high-stress tail implies that, for an equivalent drive phase, the architected geometries achieve actuation while exposing a smaller surface area to large von Mises stresses. Normalizing the motion by the average stress confirms this mechanical benefit: the figure of merit $\langle |u| \rangle_S / \langle \sigma_{VM} \rangle_S$ improves for both D1 and D2 (Table 1b). This indicates more displacement per unit of internal loading, which is consistent with safer biasing and potentially improved fatigue life.

2.5 Directionality

To ensure a consistent comparison across meshes of different densities, directionality was quantified using the same surface triangles as in the stress analysis (Sec. 2.4). Thus, the element areas $A^{(e)}$ and total surface area A_{tot} follow Eqs. (2) and (3), with quantities weighted by each triangle’s physical area. For triangle e with nodal displacements $(u_{x,i}, u_{y,i})$, $(u_{x,j}, u_{y,j})$, $(u_{x,\ell}, u_{y,\ell})$ at $t^* = 0.25$, we form element-averaged components,

$$\bar{u}_x^{(e)} = \frac{u_{x,i} + u_{x,j} + u_{x,\ell}}{3}, \quad \bar{u}_y^{(e)} = \frac{u_{y,i} + u_{y,j} + u_{y,\ell}}{3}, \quad (6)$$

and the corresponding elementwise ratio is

$$r^{(e)} \equiv \frac{|\bar{u}_y^{(e)}|}{|\bar{u}_x^{(e)}|}, \quad (7)$$

so that every surface triangle contributes one directionality value and is counted in proportion to its physical area. For any threshold τ (e.g. $\tau = 1, 2, 5, 100$), the area fraction reported in Table 1c is obtained by reusing the area-fraction form (3), but with the selection made on $r^{(e)}$:

$$\text{area-fraction}(r > \tau) = \frac{1}{A_{\text{tot}}} \sum_{e: r^{(e)} > \tau} A^{(e)}. \quad (8)$$

This definition ensures the reported percentages represent the ”percent of device surface with predominantly vertical motion” and not ”percent of mesh nodes,” which would otherwise bias the result toward the more finely meshed designs. The arrow plots in Fig. 6 show the underlying displacement directions used to build these statistics.

The resulting distributions (Fig. 7) and metrics (Table 1c) quantify the difference in motion directionality. The slab exhibits a vertical preference ($r > 1$ on $\approx 86\%$ of its area), but only

Figure 6: Displacement direction fields in (a) slab, (b) D1, and (c) D2. The length of the arrows are proportional to the $|u|$.

Figure 7: Area-weighted directionality $r = |u_y|/|u_x|$ at $t^* = 0.25$. Violins show surface-element distributions; squares/whiskers mark median/IQR; dashed line $r = 1$. Both tails trimmed by 0.5% (by area) for display.

$\approx 23\%$ of its area achieves $r > 5$, and $\approx 0.5\%$ exceeds $r > 100$. In contrast, both architected geometries show motion that is almost entirely vertical ($r > 1$ on 100% of the area; $r > 2$ on $\approx 99\%$). These designs also possess large high-directionality regions, with $r > 5$ on 61–65% of the area and $r > 100$ on $\approx 9\%$. This confirms that the geometric features responsible for stress redistribution (Sec. 2.4) also channel motion into the primary actuation axis, providing a mechanism-level explanation for the low-parasitic response.

2.6 Convergence and key design drivers

Finally, we analyze the optimization convergence and identify the most influential design variables (shown in Fig. 9). The Nelder–Mead routine converged for both architectures; the running-best objective in Figs. 8c and 8d rises monotonically and then plateaus, confirming successful maximization of the objective (Eq 11) defined in Sec. 4.

To rank the influence of each parameter on the objective, we used a correlation-based sensitivity: for each design variable x_j and objective \mathcal{J} (Eq 11), we compute the Pearson coefficient

$$r_j = \text{corr}(x_j, \mathcal{J}) = \frac{\text{cov}(x_j, \mathcal{J})}{\sigma_{x_j} \sigma_{\mathcal{J}}}, \quad (9)$$

and convert it to a unitless importance score by taking magnitude and normalizing to the largest value,

$$I_j = \frac{|r_j|}{\max_k |r_k|} \in [0, 1]. \quad (10)$$

We use $|r_j|$ because only the strength of influence is needed for ranking (the sign simply indicates whether \mathcal{J} increases or decreases with x_j).

Figs. 8a and 8b report these normalized importances. In Design 1, angular variables dominate (α_2 highest, then α_1), while t_0 and r_2 are weaker—implying performance is set mainly by angular control of compliant/field pathways. In Design 2, t_0 is the strongest driver (with θ_2 and θ_1 secondary), and r_2, θ_4, θ_5 contribute little. Practically, this analysis suggests the search can be narrowed around the dominant variables and that geometry-driven alignment—angles in Design 1, section thickness in Design 2—governs the electrostrictive response and can be used as practical tuning knobs.

Figure 8: (a,b) Normalized importance of design variables from correlation analysis with the objective. Angles (α_i, θ_i) dominate performance, whereas length parameters (t_0, r_2) contribute less. (c,d) Evolution of the objective value during Nelder–Mead iterations. The running-best curve shows a monotonic increase and saturation, confirming successful maximization.

3 Conclusion and Discussion

With identical material, drive, and analysis across all three cells, our results confirm that geometry can shape the polarization field to improve device-level electrostriction. Our architected designs preserve the expected quadratic ($\mathbf{S} \propto \mathbf{P}^2$) relation at the device scale but use it far more efficiently, increasing the effective actuation-axis coefficient (Q_{11}^{eff}) by $\sim 1.7\times$ for Design-2 and boosting the motion-per-joule by $\sim 11\text{--}16\times$ for both designs. Critically, this enhanced stroke is achieved at a significantly lower average polarization ($\sim 2.4\text{--}3.2\times$ below the slab). The metamaterial architectures also demonstrate “stress-quiet” actuation: they shift the internal stress burden away from high-stress bins and nearly double the useful stroke-per-unit-stress. This is coupled with a $\sim 3\times$ improvement in motion directionality, with 61–65% of the architected surfaces showing strongly guided motion ($r > 5$) compared to only 23% for the slab.

Limitations and Outlook The main implication is that shape can be used as a practical tuning knob to overcome inherent material-level trade-offs. This work establishes that compliant, field-routing pathways offer a reproducible route to higher motion-per-energy and, most importantly, reduced exposure to peak stresses. This architectural strategy, which is complementary to atomic-level enhancement approaches, provides a clear path toward more robust, fatigue-tolerant, high-precision devices. While this 2D, quasi-static study confirms the principle, natural next

Figure 9: Schematics of architectures with design variables that control compliant pathways in Design 1 and Design 2.

steps include (i) experimental prototyping to verify these safe-bias and directionality gains, (ii) 3D and frequency-response modeling to assess dynamic performance, and (iii) the development of array-level layouts to scale these unit-cell advantages for system-level applications.

4 Materials and Methods

Computation and physics. All simulations were performed in COMSOL MULTIPHYSICS using the *Ferroelectroelasticity* multiphysics coupling, which combines the *Solid Mechanics* and *Electrostatics* interfaces to resolve the fully coupled electrostriction response. The study used a 2D plane-strain model with quadratic serendipity elements for displacement and quadratic Lagrange elements for potential. The geometric layout, drive, boundary conditions, and averaging regions are exactly as described in Sec 2.1. Material data were held identical across the slab, Design 1 (D1), and Design 2 (D2). While Hom and Shankar report a Young’s modulus of 115 GPa and Poisson’s ratio of 0.26 [49], this study utilizes the effective simulation parameters ($E = 105$ GPa, $\nu = 0.4$) established in the standard numerical benchmark [50] to ensure direct comparability with existing numerical literature. All specific parameter values are listed in Table S1 in Supplementary Materials.

Optimization setup. The geometries were optimized in COMSOL using the *Nelder–Mead* derivative-free method, suitable for nonconvex and non-smooth responses in the coupled Electrostatics–Solid Mechanics model. The objective across the 50 phases ($0 \leq t^* \leq 0.5$; $t^* = 0, 0.01, 0.02 \dots$) maximized a direct sum of three unweighted terms:

$$\mathcal{J} = \langle |u| \rangle_S + \max_S |u| + \left\langle \|\mathbf{S}^{(\text{elec})}\|_2 \right\rangle_S, \quad (11)$$

where $|u|$ is the displacement magnitude and $\|\mathbf{S}^{(\text{elec})}\|_2$ is the electrostrictive-strain norm. Design variables (Fig. 9) define angular and length parameters that tune compliant pathways in the two architectures.

Model validation framework. The coupled ferroelectroelastic FEM implementation was validated in three steps before analyzing the architected geometries. First, we verified that the constitutive relations (polarization saturation and electrostrictive strain coupling) were implemented consistently with the Hom–Shankar phenomenology [27, 49, 51]. Second, we benchmarked our implementation against the COMSOL Application Library “Electrostrictive Disc” model using identical PMN–PT–BT parameters, comparing average P–E and S–E responses (Supplementary Sec. S2; Fig. S1). Third, we performed analytical consistency checks in the low-field regime by confirming a quadratic $S \propto E^2$ trend via an effective coefficient M_{eff} computed from the lowest non-zero field points (Supplementary Sec. S2). Detailed validation results and discussion are provided in the Supplementary Materials (Sec. S2).

Supplementary Materials

Supplementary Text

- Sec. S1: *Supplementary Methods*
 - Sec. S1.1: *Material parameters*
 - Sec. S1.2: *Full linear-fit statistics for effective electrostriction*
 - Sec. S1.3: *Full performance tables referenced by main-text Table 1*
- Sec. S2: *Simulation Model Validation*
 - Sec. S2.1: *Constitutive Model Implementation*
 - Sec. S2.2: *Validation Against COMSOL Benchmark*
 - Sec. S2.3: *Analytical Consistency Checks*

Figures

- Fig. S1: *Comparison of average P–E and S–E responses between the Slab FEM and COMSOL Disc benchmark using identical PMN–PT–BT parameters.*

Tables

- Table S1: *Material parameters for PMN–PT–BT used in all simulations.*
- Table S2: *No-intercept fits on surface-averaged channels (main-text Fig. 4): Q^{eff} , R^2 , and 95% confidence intervals.*
- Table S3: *Energy-aware motion: U_e , U_{elastic} , U_{in} , $\langle |u| \rangle_S$, and $\langle |u| \rangle_S / U_{\text{in}}$.*
- Table S4: *Actuation per stress: $\langle |u| \rangle_S$, $\langle \sigma_{\text{VM}} \rangle_S$, and $\langle |u| \rangle_S / \langle \sigma_{\text{VM}} \rangle_S$.*
- Table S5: *Directionality metrics at $t^* = 0.25$ (area-weighted), including thresholded area fractions.*

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